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In this article, we will review the most commonly used incisions and approaches, focusing on aortic valve, mitral valve, and aortocoronary bypass procedures. Surgical techniques take the lead in the treatment of coronary artery lesions. Numerous clinical trials show higher efficacy of surgical treatment. CHD in the form of myocardial revascularization by percutaneous coronary intervention compared to drug therapy alone, both in the short and long term.

Keywords: cardiac surgery, minimally invasive surgery, valve surgery**ЯРБЕКОВ Рустам Раимкулович**

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ХИРУРГИЮ (литературный обзор)**

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье нами будет рассмотрено наиболее широко используемые разрезы и подходы, уделяя особое внимание процедурам аортального клапана, митрального клапана и аортокоронарного шунтирования. Хирургические методы занимают лидирующую позицию в лечении поражения коронарных артерий. Множество клинических исследований показывает более высокую эффективность хирургического лечения. ИБС в виде реваскуляризации миокарда посредством чрезкожного коронарного вмешательства по сравнению с только медикаментозной терапией, как в краткосрочной, так и долгосрочной перспективе.

Ключевые слова: кардиохирургия, малоинвазивная хирургия, клапанная хирургия

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**MINIMAL INVAZIV KORONAR JARROHLIKNING ZAMONAVIY QARASHLARI
(ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)**

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada biz tomondan aorta klapani, mitral klapan va toj arteriyasiga oid bajaraladigan muolajalarigalariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan bo'lib, eng ko'p ishlatiladigan kesmalar va yondashuvlarni ko'rib chiqamiz. Jarrohlik usullari koronar arteriya faoliyatining buzuliishini davolashda yetakchi o'rinni egallaydi. Ko'pgina klinik tadqiqotlar jarrohlik davolashning yuqori samaradorligini ko'rsatadi. Qisqa va uzoq muddatda faqat dori terapiyasi bilan solishtirganda teri orqali koronar aralashuv orqali miokard revaskulyarizatsiyasi ko'rinishida bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: yurak jarrohligi, minimal invaziv jarrohlik, klapan jarrohligi

Introduction. Along with the broader surgical community, cardiovascular surgery is in the process of continually evolving techniques in the 1990s the world first became aware of minimally invasive valve surgery, which has influenced virtually all types of cardiac surgery performed today, which has been an evolution for cardiologists [1]. With increasing patient interest in minimally invasive procedures, it is more important than ever for surgeons to stay abreast of the most common minimally invasive techniques in cardiac surgery. In the modern era of cardiac surgery, most operations have been performed via midline sternotomy using artificial circulation. However, this paradigm is changing as minimally invasive techniques are increasingly being utilized in cardiovascular surgery. Advances in patient assessment, instrumentation, and operative techniques have allowed surgeons to perform a wide range of complex operations through smaller incisions and, in some cases, without artificial circulation. Given that patients desire less invasive surgeries and the literature supports reduced blood loss, shorter hospital stays, less postoperative pain, and better cosmetic outcomes, minimally invasive cardiac surgery should be widely practiced. In this article, we review the incisions and approaches currently used in minimally invasive cardiovascular surgery.

Hemisternotomy-Minimally invasive accesses to the aortic valve can be performed using a wide range of incisions, the most commonly used access is the hemisternotomy, usually J-shaped to the right fourth intercostal space. In this method, a midline incision is made at the sterno-manubrial junction and extended 4-5 cm downward [2]. The necessary exposure of the sternum can be achieved without enlarging the skin incision by undermining the soft tissues both above and below. A standard sternal saw is then used to divide the sternum along the midline to its smooth curve and entrance into the fourth intercostal space. Although extending the incision to the fourth intercostal space is the most common approach, the specific intercostal space used can and should be customized to the patient[4].

For example, suitable exposure may be possible using the third intercostal space in a lean patient, whereas the fifth space may be required in an obese patient. Aortic root exposure is also possible with a sternotomy in the fifth intercostal space, making this access useful in a wide range of aortic valve and aortic root surgeries. After crossing the sternum and dissecting the mediastinal tissues, a vertical pericardiotomy is performed and the edges of the pericardium are sutured to the skin. This allows complete anterior retraction of the mediastinum and maximizes exposure of the aorta[5].

One advantage of the hemisternotomy is that it allows a variety of cannulation strategies, from completely central to purely peripheral. Columbia University uses standard centrally placed cannulas for the ascending aorta and right atrium, as well as drainage of the right superior pulmonary vein and, if desired, a retrograde catheter for cardioplegia[7]. This method is used in total sternotomy surgery, it minimizes the number of new techniques that must be learned to perform the procedure successfully.

Exposure and visualization can be maximized by withdrawing the venous cannula inferolaterally, suturing through the chest wall with a needle hook, using low-profile aortic cross-clamps, and placing the patient in a steep reverse Trendelenburg position. Despite this, cannulation can also be performed through the femoral artery and vein by placing a pulmonary artery vent or retrograde cardioplegia catheter peripherally from the neck. Completely peripheral cannulation minimizes potential obstructions in the operative field, but requires considerable experience on the part of the anesthesia and perfusion teams[9]. Some reports suggest that taking cannulation to the periphery of the field provides adequate visualization and workspace without the additional technical challenges associated with peripheral cannulation. Once cannulation is achieved, the remainder of the operation is performed in a standardized manner[10].

Right anterior thoracotomy-Another minimally invasive access to the aortic valve is the right anterior thoracotomy. This operation is more commonly used for mitral valve surgery, but it can also be used for aortic valve surgery, which avoids sternotomy, and provides less exposure because the aortic root and valve are more difficult to see and reach from this angle. Right anterior thoracotomy usually requires more sophisticated and active monitoring via esophageal echocardiography at least for peripheral cannulation and in some cases for peripheral insertion of retrograde cardioplegia catheters or pulmonary vein ventilation [8].

The technique of right anterior thoracotomy is performed using a 4-6 cm long incision is made along the medial surface of the right third intercostal space, dissecting the underlying tissue and entering the pleural cavity [2]. Because of the medial incision, ligation of the right internal mammary vessels is usually required at this stage, and separation of the third or fourth rib from the sternum may be necessary to ensure adequate exposure. The pericardium is then opened anteriorly from the diaphragmatic nerve and a pericardiotomy is performed to the diaphragm below and to the pericardium above. A cannula for antegrade cardioplegia is inserted directly through the primary incision, and a transthoracic aortic transverse clamp is inserted through the stab incision, after which the disconnected rib is sutured to the sternum. The surgeon should consider the frequent need for rib-cartilage disarticulation and rib fractures that are associated with this access [3].

Operations performed on the mitral valve- Right parasternal access for minimally invasive mitral valve surgery was used by some authors. Several years later, other cardiac surgeons performed via right-sided thoracotomy, where alternative approaches such as hemisternotomy, left thoracotomy and right minithoracotomy were developed; of these, right-sided minithoracotomy is the most widely used in current clinical practice [4].

Right minithoracotomy is recognized as the most commonly used incision in minimally invasive mitral valve surgery and is now the standard minimally invasive access in most centers. Several retrospective studies have evaluated outcomes after mitral valve surgery via right minithoracotomy. Benefits including a better view of the valve, reduced risk of infection due to the well-vascularized superior pectoralis muscle and lack of sternal separation, shorter hospitalization. stay, less postoperative bleeding, and less postoperative pain [6].

To access the mitral valve through right-sided minithoracotomy, an inframammary incision of 4-6 cm in length along the mid axillary line is made for primary access and supplemented with stab

incisions if necessary [7]. This primary incision is made 1-2 cm below the nipple in men and approximately 1 cm above the breast crease in women, followed by soft tissue dissection directed cranially to the chest wall to allow access to the chest cavity through the fourth intercostal space. The incision is usually made medially to minimize the working distance to the valve, but not as medially as in aortic valve surgery, shifting the incision slightly laterally results in a wider view of the valve but at the expense of greater surface distance. The ideal location to maximize working distance and visualization of the valve can be altered according to the surgeon's preference. Once the primary incision is made, stab incisions are used to introduce accessory instruments [8]. In our practice, two small stab incisions are made a few intercostal spaces below the primary incision to guide the carbon dioxide insufflator and suction pump during the procedure and the pleural drainage tube afterward. If desired, a 5 or 8 mm videoscope can be introduced through one or more incisions, both of which are located along the anterior axillary line. To improve exposure of the heart, the right hemisphere of the diaphragm is withdrawn downward by suturing its tendinous dome and bringing it to the skin through the seventh to eighth interval with a needle-hook apparatus [9].

The pericardium is then opened, starting a few centimeters anteriorly from the right diaphragmatic nerve, and the pericardiotomy is continued down to the diaphragm and up to the ascending aorta. The anterior edge of the pericardium is withdrawn with sutures to the medial aspect of the skin incision, and the posterior edge is withdrawn with sutures brought to the skin with a needle hook. A transthoracic Chitwood clamp is then inserted through the stab wound in the third interval along the right medial axillary line and prepared for possible atrial retraction by inserting a retractor through the chest wall medial to the primary incision. This retractor may be self-retaining, as in devices that attach directly to the chest wall with screw clamps, or may be held in place with table clamps [10]. Although cannulation during artificial circulation can be performed in a completely peripheral fashion. Similar to minimally invasive aortic surgery, the use of central cannulation minimizes both the number of new techniques required to adopt the entire procedure and the expertise required of other members of the surgical team, such as anesthesia and perfusion. In particular, avoiding peripheral artery cannulation and endoaortic balloon occlusion not only simplifies and shortens the procedure, but also eliminates the risk of complications such as retrograde aortic dissection, retroperitoneal hemorrhage, and lower extremity ischemia [1].

In minithoracotomy, cannulas for aortic, superior vena cava, antegrade cardioplegia, and retrograde cardioplegia can be placed centrally through the primary incision, leaving only the inferior vena cava cannula to be placed peripherally. Some surgeons perform a multistage venous cannula through the femoral vein using the Seldinger technique under PEE control, supplementing, if necessary, with a standard rectangular cannula inserted through the primary incision into the superior vena cava. In reviewing the various literature, we believe that although this degree of central cannulation reduces the technical complexity and simplifies the entire process, it still creates the potential for difficulty in visualization or movement during the procedure. Other authors believe that cannulation involves a fully peripheral and hybrid design, with the aortic and venous cannulas placed in the periphery and the cannulas for antegrade and retrograde cardioplegia remaining in the center [2].

After cannulation of the patient and initiation of artificial circulation, mitral valve exposure can be started with dissection of Sondergaard's sulcus. Once the aorta is clamped, the left atrium is opened and the anterior left atrium and septum are retracted forward using one of the types of retractors described above. One technique that helps to maximize visualization is to place a retraction suture mainly using 3-0 monofilament, approximately one centimeter from the P3 portion of the mitral annulus in the inferior wall of the left atrium [3]. This suture is then led out of the left atrium, behind the inferior vena cava (through the oblique sinus) and out of the thorax laterally. This serves both to drain the excess inferior wall of the left atrium away from the valve and to improve the view of the inferior valve. Other work by cardiac surgeons where used a similar technique placing the transthoracic retractor as close to the sternum as possible to prevent the left atrium from sliding off the retractor and away from the surgeon. Paying special attention to the left internal mammary artery, which may be injured by this maneuver, the valve is approximated a few centimeters by placing

several thick sutures on the posterior aspect of the mitral annulus, as is done during annuloplasty, and attaching them to the surgical band. After detection, valve repair or replacement is performed in the standard manner of valve replacement, the atriotomy is closed in the standard manner and cardiac deaeration is performed under ChEE monitoring[4].

There is much debate about de-aeration in minimally invasive surgery, which is the use of carbon dioxide insufflation in each case followed by an extensive de-aeration protocol performed under the supervision of a ChPE that involves positioning the patient in deep Trendelenburg during aortic unclamping, aggressive cardiac volume loading, positive pressure ventilation to clear pulmonary venous air, and alternating left and right table positions to remove air trapped beneath the interventricular septum. After de-aeration, electrodes for cardiac pacing are placed, local nerve blockade is applied, and the chest is closed[5].

Robot-assisted mitral valve surgery

The history of foreign colleagues in the development of telemanipulation technology in the 1990s paved the way for robotic valve surgery, and in 1998 Karpente i Mor independently reported the first cases of robotic mitral valve plasty. The technique evolved rapidly, and over the next 2 years Mexmlesh and colleagues performed the first closed endoscopic mitral valve plasty, Grossi and colleagues performed posterior leaflet repair, and Chitvud and colleagues performed posterior leaflet resection followed by reconstruction. and annuloplasty [6]. In addition to the potential benefits of minimally invasive surgery, multiple groups have reported additional advantages of robotic surgery, including three-dimensional visualization, ambidextrous, tremor filtering, motion scaling, and even smaller incisions. Outcomes after robotic mitral valve surgery in a prospective multicenter phase II trial involving 112 patients showed an 8% incidence of postoperative grade 2 mitral regurgitation and a 5.4% reoperation rate. Columbia University Medical Center used in the first US trial of robotic mitral valve surgery and is currently performing the procedure developed by Professor Chitwood via a 5-6 cm right submammary minithoracotomy that enters the chest through the fourth intercostal space [2]. This incision is similar to that used in the previously described minithoracotomy, and intrathoracic preparation in our center is performed in the same way. As discussed previously, cannulation during artificial circulation can be peripheral or central. Aortic occlusion can be performed either by transthoracic aortic clamping or by endoaortic balloon with continuous carbon dioxide insufflation into the operating field. Typically, two robotic arms are inserted into the chest through 10-mm trocar incisions[1]. The right instrument is inserted 4-6 cm lateral to the thoracotomy site in the fourth or fifth intercostal space, and the left instrument is placed medial and cranial to the right instrument in the second or third intercostal space. A distance of 6 cm is maintained between the levers, and the alignment of the levers with the valve plane is optimized to allow unrestricted movement of the instruments[7]. A 30-degree stereoscopic endoscope is introduced through the medial portion of the thoracotomy, leaving the remaining portion of the incision as a working port for the assistant on the patient's side. If desired, the third arm can also be used as a dynamic retractor. When the patient is on artificial circulation, the left atrium is accessed using a left atriotomy along the interatrial sulcus, and the valve is exposed using a transthoracic intraatrial retractor. Valve repair, atriotomy closure, disconnection from artificial circulation, de-aeration and closure can then be performed in the usual manner[3].

Aortocoronary bypass surgery (ACB) is a major surgical procedure in which atheromatous blockages in a patient's coronary arteries are bypassed using retrieved venous or arterial conduits. Bypass surgery restores blood flow to the ischemic myocardium, which in turn restores function, vitality and manages the symptoms of angina pectoris. There are several different types of bypass procedures.

In general, ACS surgical procedures with and without bypass are two types of ACS surgical procedures, the difference being the use of the bypass and cardiac arrest circuitry to operate during ACS with bypass. The conduits used as bypass grafts are usually left internal thoracic artery and saphenous vein grafts from the lower extremities.

Other conduits that can be transplanted include (right internal thoracic artery, radial artery, and gastric-sacral artery. The type and location of the grafts depend on the patient's anatomy and the

location of the occluded arteries. Typically, the left internal thoracic artery is grafted to the left anterior descending artery, and other conduits are used for other occluded arteries. In preparation for surgery, the patient will need several tests in addition to coronarography that diagnoses coronary heart disease. They will need laboratory tests such as a general blood count (GBC), metabolic panels including liver function tests, coagulation panels and hemoglobin. Other tests may be required including electrocardiogram (ECG), echocardiogram, ultrasound of the carotid arteries, chest x-ray and possibly chest CT or lower extremity vein mapping.

Preoperative medications such as beta-blockers are most often continued throughout the preoperative period to prevent arrhythmias such as atrial fibrillation. Previously, aspirin was stopped 5-7 days before surgery, but more recently it is recommended that it be started or continued until surgery.

On admission to the hospital, the patient will be started on intravenous access and their medications and preoperative labs will be checked. Hair will be trimmed at the surgical site and the patient will be given a chlorhexidine bath.

The procedure begins once the patient is in the operating room and connected to standard monitors. Prior to induction of general anesthesia, the anesthesiologist can establish an arterial line for invasive monitoring of the patient's blood pressure. After induction of general anesthesia and intubation of the patient, a central venous access line and pulmonary artery catheter can be placed, followed by insertion of a transesophageal echocardiography transducer. The patient is sterilely prepared and covered, and a break is made before the surgical incision is made. A midline sternotomy is performed by the surgeon to prepare for removal of the left internal thoracic artery for use as a guide, the assistant, simultaneously removes the saphenous vein from one or both legs using open or video-assisted techniques. Once suitable guides are acquired, the surgeon administers anticoagulants, most commonly heparin, to prepare for artificial circulation. The patient's aorta and heart are cannulated centrally, and a tube is connected to the artificial circulation circuit. Once artificial circulation is initiated, the heart is stopped with high-potassium cardioplegia to allow the surgeon to anastomose the retrieved conduits to the coronary arteries distal to the occlusions. After the surgeon anastomoses distally, the conduits are attached to new holes created in the proximal aorta. The cardioplegia is then eroded, the heart begins to contract, and the surgeon can check the grafts for circulation and function, as well as check for bleeding from the anastomosis sites. The chest is then sutured with sternal spokes and the patient is transferred to the intensive care unit for monitoring hemodynamic stability and extubation.

One type of bypass surgery that may be recommended is called off-pump coronary artery bypass surgery.

Off-pump coronary artery bypass (OPCAB), also called "beating heart" surgery, is an operation to treat narrowed or blocked coronary arteries. This is accomplished by bypassing or "bypassing" the blocked artery with a healthy vessel called a "graft" that is taken from the leg, arm, or chest. The graft will now spread blood around the blockage, improving blood flow to the heart muscle.

Traditionally, aortocoronary bypass surgery is performed when the heart stops and a heart-lung pump is used. The function of the pump is to oxygenate the blood and circulate blood during cardiac arrest. This is called artificial circulation or CPB. Because there are certain risks associated with artificial circulation, specially trained cardiothoracic surgeons now perform "off-pump" bypass surgery, that is, without a bypass machine.

OPCAB surgery is open heart surgery performed without artificial circulation (CPB) and with the heart still working. "Open heart surgery" is a general term used in reference to aortocoronary bypass surgery. Many people believe that the heart "opens" during "open heart surgery". However, this is not true. The name actually refers to the fact that the surgery is performed through a large open chest incision. Because the surgery is actually performed on blood vessels on the outside of the heart, there is no need to open the heart.

Some surgeons perform minimally invasive coronary artery bypass grafting (MICABG) surgery through tiny incisions called portals, which allows for a shorter recovery time and less trauma to tissue and bone.

Non-assisted coronary bypass surgery is performed by cardiothoracic surgeons in the operating room with the patient under general anesthesia. The surgery usually takes about 3 hours, but can be longer depending on the number of bypass anastomoses. During OPCAB, the patient is placed on the operating table lying supine. The chest and graft area are shaved and treated with antiseptic, and a general anesthetic will be given so you can sleep and feel no pain. The surgeon will make a long incision in the middle of your breastbone (sternum). At the same time, another surgeon will "harvest" (remove) a vessel from your arm (radial artery) or leg (long saphenous vein) to use as a graft. This can be done through a large "open" incision or endoscopically through a much smaller incision. The surgeon may choose to use an artery in the chest called the internal thoracic artery. In this case, you will not have a "graft site" incision in your arm or leg unless you have multiple shunts. A special device is used to stabilize the heart muscle on either side of the blockage. This allows the surgeon to work on a small area with minimal movement, but the heart is still beating and pumping blood throughout the body. If a leg or arm graft is used, the surgeon then attaches one end of the graft with thin stitches to the aorta. The other end of the graft is then attached to the coronary artery outside the blockage. This allows blood to "bypass" the blockage and flow freely to the heart muscle. If the internal thoracic artery is used, the surgeon will reroute the artery by detaching one end of the graft and reattaching it below the site of the blockage in the coronary artery. After the operator has performed the required number of bypass shunts, the surgeon will reattach the sternum with a wire and close the incision, usually with absorbable sutures. [7].

Minimally invasive direct aortocoronary bypass (MIDCAB) provides arterial revascularization of the left anterior descending coronary artery, especially in lesions unsuitable for percutaneous coronary interventions. Avoiding sternotomy and artificial circulation, its invasiveness is less than that of conventional bypass surgery.

Minimally invasive direct aortocoronary artery bypass grafting (MIDCAB) into the spectrum of surgical revascularization this method has been further developed. Today, it is a representative part of the cardiac surgical program at some institutions. The procedure is considered less invasive than traditional aortocoronary bypass (ACH) or off-pump revascularization (OPCAB) and is close to percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI). MIDCAB can be considered as an alternative treatment option besides well-established revascularization procedures. MIDCAB has been mainly used in patients with proximal stenosis of the left anterior descending artery (LAD). In these patients, interventional PCI is often risky or impossible due to complex lesions, close interaction with the main trunk or other coronary arteries, or complete occlusion of the target vessel. In other patients, repeated interventions on the PMLV have remained without lasting success. In addition to its original purpose for PMLV revascularization, MIDCAB may be a useful part of hybrid procedures in patients with multivessel disease in whom extensive coronary surgery is poorly tolerated. Although multivessel disease is a predictor of increased mortality after ACS, the MIDCAB procedure can be performed as a stand-alone procedure with acceptable results in mid-term morbidity and mortality, even though formally incomplete revascularization may remain [4]. Several studies and our own experience have proven that MIDCAB can be safely performed in selected patients with main trunk stenosis or multivessel lesions [5]. Complete revascularization can be achieved by a hybrid approach with concomitant PCI. The patient is placed under general anesthesia and intubated with a double-lumen tube. Standard monitoring includes a 5-lead electrocardiogram (ECG), measurement of blood pressure, central venous pressure, nasopharyngeal temperature, and peripheral oxygen saturation. The main features of the procedure consist of a small left anterior thoracotomy in the fourth or fifth intercostal space. The pleural cavity is opened and the left lung is deflated to facilitate graft extraction. The left internal thoracic artery is harvested on a stalk to the level of the first rib. A chest wall tilt device attached to the upper rib is useful to reach the proximal portions of the left internal thoracic artery. After collection is completed, this artery is dissected distally at the level of the sixth intercostal space. Graft perfusion is monitored, and local application of papaverine as a vasodilator may optimize graft flow. After

pericardial dissection and fractional sutures, the target site is partially immobilized with a special mechanical stabilizer. Before PMNV occlusion, 100 IU/kg of unfractionated heparin is administered. In almost every case, preconditioning is utilized by temporary occlusion of the PMNV using 4-0 tourniquets applied over silicone tubing. After a short period of reperfusion, the target vessel is cut. The field is cleared of blood with a humidified blower using fluid and carbon dioxide. Anastomosis between the left internal thoracic artery and the PMLV is performed under visual inspection with 8/0 monofilament, with the first five sutures spaced apart. In contrast to the other groups, videoscapy as well as intracoronary bypass are not used. After completion of the anastomosis, the stem is fixed with two sutures to avoid graft torsion. Once blood flow is restored, heparin is counteracted with protamine. The initially mobilized prepericardial fatty tissue is fixed to the medial pericardium to cover the distal part of the VMA. An inferior posterior pleural drainage tube is placed in the left pleural cavity. Thoracotomy closure, including 2 transcostal sutures, must be performed with extreme care to avoid graft-to-chest wall contact or herniation of mediastinal structures. All patients are expected to be extubated inpatient and have a short stay in the intensive care unit.

Conclusions: In summary, since the 1990s, minimally invasive techniques have been applied to a wide range of cardiac surgeries. Over the past two decades, numerous sources have demonstrated the feasibility, safety, and efficacy of minimally invasive cardiac surgery and supported its integration into clinical practice. With the advent of minimally invasive cardiac surgery, its popularity and experience has increased significantly. Various methods of obtaining appropriate exposure have been developed and put into practice. Regardless of the variety of surgical approaches, the overall goals of minimally invasive cardiac surgery remain the same, to provide a safe and effective approach with the advantages inherent in minimal access surgery. As with many surgical techniques, patients with special risks are the best candidates for certain techniques. A patient-centered approach should be taken when selecting different approaches. The difficult learning curve of minimally invasive cardiac surgery, the central concepts of introducing new techniques and technologies should always include initially selecting uncomplicated patients, creating a consistent operative team, and following modular and staged approaches in order to increase complexity and reduce skin incision. Minimally invasive cardiac surgery is feasible and reproducible. An increase in patient requests for minimally invasive cardiac surgery seems inevitable. It should not only be an alternative to traditional cardiac surgery, but also a standard of care in experienced hands.

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